

Funded by
the European Union

Ref. Ares(2024)4731346 - 01/07/2024
PROSPLIGN

Prospecting natural lignin biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules

The PROSPLIGN project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Programme of the European Union under Grant Agreement n° 101135298.

WP1

KELADA

D1.2-Preliminary Data Management Plan

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101135298	Acronym	PROSPLIGN	
Full Title	Prospecting natural lignin biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules.			
Start Date	01/01/2024	Duration	3 years	
Project Website	www.prosplign.eu			
Deliverable	D1.2- Preliminary Data Management Plan			
Work Package	WP1			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/12/2026	Actual	28/06/2024
Type	DMP	Dissemination Level	PU	
Lead Beneficiary	KELADA			
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Contributions from	Jessica Whelan and Abdoulah Ly (UCD), Malachi Gillick-Healy (KELADA)			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Description	Contributor
1.0	17/05/2024	Draft outline and DMP forms created and sent to UCD	Malachi Gillick-Healy (KELADA)
2.0	30/05/2024	Contributions from partners requested	Jessica Whelan and Abdoulah Ly (UCD)
3.0	17/06/2024	Full draft integrating contributions collected from all partners respective DMP forms circulated to consortium for review/comment	Jessica Whelan and Abdoulah Ly (UCD), Malachi Gillick-Healy (KELADA)
4.0	26/06/2024	Revised version addressing consortium member's comments and suggestions. Sent to coordinator for review	Jessica Whelan and Abdoulah Ly (UCD)
5.0	26/06/2024	Feedback and final adjustments sent to UCD by coordinator	Malachi Gillick-Healy (KELADA)
6.0	28/06/2024	Final version sent to coordinator for final review and submission	Jessica Whelan and Abdoulah Ly (UCD)
7.0	28/06/2024	Submitted version	Malachi Gillick-Healy (KELADA)

Nature of Deliverable	
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
OTHER	Software, technical diagrams, algorithms, models, etc.
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.
DMP	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues

Dissemination level	
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
Classified EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No 2015/444
Classified EU-C	CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No 2015/444
Classified EU-S	EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No 2015/444

Acronym/Abbreviations	
CA	Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement (contractual document between EC and beneficiaries)
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
CPP	Critical Process Parameters
CMA	Critical Material Attributes
CQA	Critical Quality Attributes
SW	Software
WP	Work Package
MVDA	Multivariate Data Analysis
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
TEA	Technico-Economic- Assessment
HPLC	High Performance Liquid Chromatography
GC	Gas Chromatography
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
DOI/ORCID	Digital Object Identifier/Open Research and Contributor ID
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry

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1. Executive summary

This document presents the **Preliminary Data Management Plan** for the PROSPLIGN project and outlines several points in connection with the management and governance of data arising from the different Work Packages (WP) activities. The Data Management Plan (**DMP**) depicts the basic guidelines for the partners and different stakeholders as it gives some answers concerning the data generation processes (purpose, types and formats, origin etc.). Furthermore, it portrays the **FAIR** (**F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**e-usable) principles as recommended by the **EU**'s open science policy guidelines (**Article 16 Annex 5**).

Various kinds of data will be collected during the project, including reports (dissemination, meetings...), research data, research material (samples, bioproducts, molecules, strains, enzymes) and processes (optimized production routes and methods) as well as software related material (algorithms, protocols, models, workflow and electronic notebook).

The **DMP** narrates how the **FAIR** principles will be implemented and then facilitate data discovery for scientists and the public, contributing to a wider accessibility and re-use. Online repository channels inclusive of the **PROSPLIGN** website and scientific journals will play a key role in the dissemination of the research data. It is worth mentioning that the **DMP** is a flexible document as information can be added and/or altered during the project; and this flexibility concerns also data availability and accessibility (data initially open accessible may be restricted). All data might not be open accessible due to Intellectual Properties Rights (**IPR**). Consequently, to align with **IPR** measures, data will be "*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*" for the purposes of exploitation. Data confidentiality aspects lead to some concerns related to data security and storage; this topic will be outlined in this document. Data being made openly accessible for the purpose of a broader reuse; quality assurance processes will be a very important topic to be discussed in this **DMP** together with the delay-timeline for data availability during the PROSPLIGN project and thereafter.

Finally, this document will treat some ethical concerns (if applicable) regarding the data generated during the project, the resources allocated to the research data and other research outputs that can result from the **PROSPLIGN** project.

2. Description of the deliverable objectives and content

The **PROSPLIGN** project is a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action (**HE-RIA**) that has been accepted for funding by the European Research Executive Agency with the EU's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (**HE/2021-2027**), under the Grant Agreement (**GA**) n°**101135298**.

Its main goals are to (see **Figure 1**):

- Map "lignin biodiversity"
- Design chemical and enzymatic methods to liberate and isolate small bioactive molecules from lignin
- Verify and validate small molecule bioactivity via high-throughput methods

PROSPLIGN will achieve various advances in the prospecting framework while generating data in a wide range of R&D activities. The main breakthroughs expected are those following:

- Enhanced understanding of terrestrial biodiversity and the limits and potential of its valorization
- Address the need of sustainability sourcing and development of novel natural, sustainable and eco-friendly materials and product ingredients for the pharmaceutical, cosmetics and fragrance industries
- Improved sustainable exploitation, cultivation and processing methods based on promising species/organisms and chosen processes routes and protocols leading to a diminished pressure on the natural resources
- Increased competitiveness of European biotechnology, in particular the small and medium-sized enterprises (**SMEs**) sector
- Increased public knowledge and awareness of connections between biodiversity and biotechnology and its potentials, leading to increased trust in the scientific approaches based on informed and robust communication and mutual-learning efforts.

During the project, **PROSPLIGN** will generate data in a wide range of R&D activities (See **Table 1** - table of datasets).

Figure 1 : PROSPLIGN Concept for bioactive bioprospecting within natural lignocellulosic biodiversity

PROSPLIGN will comply with the FAIR (data must be **findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable**) principles as recommended in the Article 16 Annex 5 (GA), However, due to confidentiality and security concerns some research data will not be made openly accessible as primary data but in a processed form. Some results from PROSPLIGN activities will provide the critical steps towards further research and innovation, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating manufacturing and marketing products or processes (Article 16 Annex 5 Grant Agreement). This will apply only to those results with clear commercial interests when agreed by the General Assembly under the consortium agreement rules and conditions. Article 17 of Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement will be adapted on a case-to-case basis to cover all aspects of the work, due to confidentiality and security concerns.

The PROSPLIGN project will however comply with the “*open access requirements for scientific publications*” set out in Article 17 of Annex 5 (GA) and the consortium considers the data management actions a priority.

The project has included **Preliminary (D1.2 - this deliverable) and Final (D1.4 - due on M30) Data Management Plan (DMP) deliverables** in its Work Plan, which) detail how PROSPLIGN will collect, share and protect the data produced by the beneficiaries.

More specifically, as part of making research FAIR, the DMP will detail datasets and describe:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project,
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated,
- which methodology and standards will be applied,
- whether data will be shared/made open access and,
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

This DMP is a “**dynamic**” document and this first version, delivered at the end of Month 6 (M6), will therefore be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as (but

not limited to): **new data; changes in how data are viewed, for example new innovation potential and the decision to file a patent; and changes in consortium composition and external factors, such as members leaving or joining.** These changes should be reviewed and approved during a General Assembly meeting, as described above.

This DMP will also be reviewed in line with the interim and periodic evaluation/assessment of the project, as well as the Mid-Term and Final Reviews.

3.Data summary

- **What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?**

The specific objectives outlined correspond to the Work Packages outlined in Figure 2 which shows the relationship between the different WPs.

Specific Objective O1: Map “lignin biodiversity” and procurement of a vast range of European lignin sources.

The purpose of data generation related to the Specific Objective **O1** is to map lignin biodiversity and sources. Data from at least nine (9) lignin types will be sourced and categorized during the **WP2** activities. This will be performed by identifying and measuring characteristic data of sourced lignin and exploiting this data to support effective depolymerization of lignin in **WP3**.

Specific Objective O2: Design (chemical and enzymatic) methods to liberate and isolate small bioactive molecules from lignin.

Data will be generated from the chemical and enzymatic lignin depolymerisation methods to liberate and isolate small bioactive molecules from lignin. These datasets will be contribute to refine the link between the critical process parameters and the lignin characteristics. The enzymatic and chemical depolymerization process data arising from WP3, in addition to the sourced lignin characterisation data from WP2 may be combined with available spectroscopic data for input into the multivariate data analysis (**MVDA**) within the **WP3**. MVDA will utilize the data generated to develop a predictive decision support tool to help the bioprospecting activities and accelerate the experimental work being undertaken. The tool will inform process synthesis, design, planning and optimization. These activities will facilitate the unlocking of value-added bioactive chemicals from lignin. MVDA will be the bridge between lignin sourcing, depolymerization methods and bioactivity/functional performance and will support the identification and understanding of the relationships and dependencies of interrelated parameters (**WP2, WP3, WP5**).

Specific Objective O3: Verify bioactivity profiles of small molecules and their derivatives in pharmaceutical, cosmetics and fragrances applications.

Data generated from the bioactivity screenings in WP4 will be used to determine the bioactivity profiles of mixtures of compounds derived from lignin depolymerisation (**WP3**). After purification of individual bioactive molecules (**WP4**), high-throughput methods will be used to identify their bioactivity profiles to validate their suitability for application in pharmaceutical, cosmetics and fragrances applications (**WP5**).

Specific Objective O4: Propose innovative production methods and confirm their Environmental (LCA) and Economic (TEA) sustainability in their path towards impactful exploitation.

Corresponding to **WP6**, data arising from Life Cycle Assessment (**LCA**) and Techno Economic Assessment (**TEA**) will be used to evaluate the environmental and economic sustainability of innovative production routes which will be developed in WP5. Data generated in **WP6** will support the investigation of the environmental, climate and safety/health impact of the processes developed in WP3-5.

Figure 2: PROSPLIGN PERT chart

- **What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?**

Datasets corresponding to the practical **research activities** in specific work packages WP2-6 are outlined below and a summary of the data types/formats to be generated or re-used are outlined in **Table 1**. The following file formats are commonly used by activities in all WPs: Microsoft Office suite SW (.xls, .csv, docx, .ppt, .txt), .pdf.

WP2 - Sourcing and characterisation of biomass for lignin bioprospecting. Datasets related to the sourcing activities, as well as lignin characterization. MVDA will be applied to the data generated from

WP2 to support optimising of depolymerisation yields from WP3 and bioactivity profiles of resulting depolymerised lignin mixtures in WP4.

WP3 - Lignin chemical and enzymatic depolymerization. Datasets arising from chemical depolymerisation of lignin include reaction process parameters required for the lignin depolymerisation; Spectroscopic and general characterisation data of all compounds produced; and literature metadata used as evidence to build the conceptual framework which will underpin synthetic plans. Enzymatic depolymerisation of lignin datasets include enzyme characterization results and enzyme activities. MVDA activities will generate models, statistical analysis (e.g. ANOVA tables), charts (scores and loadings plots, variable contribution model, prediction curves etc.).

WP4 - Bioactive molecules screening and purification. WP4 involves the screening and purification of bioactive molecules resulting from the lignin chemical and enzymatic depolymerization. Purification include UV chromatograms, liquid chromatography method data; while characterisation will include nuclear magnetic resonance data and mass spectrometry data for the analysis of molecular structures.

WP5 - Derivatization, final validation of bioactives and production process design. WP5 will deal with the development of the final steps of the entire “bioprospecting +screening + production” process, to obtain tailored bioactive compounds for the target markets (pharmaceutical, fragrances and cosmetic application), and designing optimal production routes via innovative approaches.

WP6 - Environmental, economic and sustainability evaluation, safety and compliance assessment. WP6 will assess economics, sustainability, safety of the final bioactive compounds obtained and their associated envisioned production process. This WP will generate: **i)** Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) data, **ii)** documentation related to biodiversity preservation assurance and compliance.

Table 1: Data type and format generated from WP2-6

Contributing Partners	Relevant WP	Data types	Data formats
KELADA, UCD	WP2, WP3, WP5	Reaction parameters, samples characterization data (spectroscopic and chromatographic), literature metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .fid, .mnova
UCD	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	Text, data management plan (DMP), analytical experiments, Raw chemical process and bioprocess data, Enzymatic activities and kinetic measurements, Statistical data, process simulation, MVDA models,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .py, .mat, .usp (SIMCA suite) and SAS files (.jmp) • PNG, JPEG, GIF • .apw and .apwz (Aspen Plus files)

Contributing Partners	Relevant WP	Data types	Data formats
		SIMCA eduPack scripts and/or SAS, Matlab/Python codes, processed data. Life Cycle Assessment data	
UH	WP3 and WP5	Genetic material sequencing and cloning, enzymatic characterization, graphical data on enzymatic activities, microbial strains information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • .TIF, .JPG, .EPS, .prism, .dna, .wsp, • Physical strains and DNA, physical enzymes, chemical compounds
NOVA	WP4	Textual, presentation, tables, images, e-nose signals, computational scripts, signal processing files.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JPEG, GIF, TIFF, .raw, photoshop files (.psd), .bmp, .PNG • Python (.py), Jupyter Notebook (.ipynb), JavaScript Object Notation (json), Origin (.opju), RStudio (.r)
MEDINA	WP4, WP5	IC50 and concentrations from biological cytotoxicity assays	<i>see common formats above</i>
BFH	WP2, WP4	Textual and research data (Chromatograms, LC method data and NMR)	<i>see common formats above</i>

WP1 - Project Management Data. The data arising from the project management activities are summarized below:

DATASET: Project Management Data (WP1, Owners: KELADA, Coordinator and All Partners)	
DATA SUMMARY	
Purpose of the Data	The management data collected over the 36-month project aims to efficiently manage and monitor the project, in particular in terms of project planning, resource allocation, task scheduling and progress measurement.

DATASET: Project Management Data (WP1, Owners: KELADA, Coordinator and All Partners)

Type-Format of data	Different data types will be collected:		
	Data type	Format	Types of documents
	Textual data	Plain text (MS word, Pdf, PowerPoint)	- Deliverable reports, interim/periodic reports - Presentations at conferences, project/partner meetings - Meeting minutes
	Tabular data	MS Excel	- Dashboard: the one central place where the Project Coordinator and all partners can see all information about the project: Action calendar, Partner list and contact details, Gantt, deliverables, milestones, reporting calendar, list of meetings, list of actions; - Key Performance Indicators - Table of resources, person-months
Image data	JPEG, PDF	Tables, figures, diagrams, etc.	
Reused-Data	No		
Data origin	<p>Reference documents: Most of the management data comes from official documents (EC reference documents, guidelines, reporting/deliverable templates, etc.) completed by project partners.</p> <p>Data is generated by all Partners who all contribute to the Project's Management activities to ensure that the project objectives and deliverables are reached on scope and in-time.</p>		
Data size	<p>The dataset will grow over the project's duration as new information becomes available. The number of deliverables reports, interim/periodic reports and publications will increase as the project goes.</p> <p>The dataset is also revisable. If a new version of the deliverable or milestone is available, the previous version is archived.</p>		
Data Security and Storage	<p>The generated/consolidated data will be stored on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROSPLIGN Sharepoint, a secured web platform dedicated to collaborative project management, administered and hosted by KELADA. • Partners' secured servers company that are automatically backed-up 		
Data value (Long Term)	<p>All data is useful to the project partners (e.g. to match time-lines or schedules for joint activities).</p> <p>All public reports or presentations can be useful to other stakeholders.</p>		
Making data FINDABLE, including provisions for metadata			
Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	<p>During the course of the project, the reports and deliverables are reported and named following the guidelines set in the XXXX</p>		
Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	<p>Management data will be named as mentioned below, following internal/consortium rules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E.g. at KELADA, internal data can be clearly identified by file name and KELADA internal project management directory structure. 		

DATASET: Project Management Data (WP1, Owners: KELADA, Coordinator and All Partners)

Naming conventions used	See Table 3
Clear versioning approach	All documents, including deliverables, reports and minutes, etc., have a tracking feature in the template to ensure versions can be easily monitored. Versioning of the documents is also given automatically by the partners' internal standards.
Making DATA openly ACCESSIBLE	
Data openly available or kept close	The full management dataset will be confidential and only made available to the consortium. If it is decided that the restricted dataset should become openly accessible, a specific data portal will be created on the secure collaborative platform. A description of the dataset and link to a download section will be provided.
How data will be made available	Not applicable
Access restrictions	By default, the full data is restricted to the consortium. All data will be made available to partners on the PROSPLIGN Sharepoint platform. The data access restriction is managed by the CA .
Making data INTEROPERABLE	
Data interoperability assessment	See Section 4.3
Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	
Data licensing for wide reuse	
Increase data RE-USE (through clarifying licenses)	
Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	See Section 4.4 - Increase data RE-USE
Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	To be defined on a case-by-case basis according to general rules defined in CA
Restrictions to data re-use	The full dataset will be kept confidential and only made accessible to consortium members for confidentiality reasons. The data access restriction is managed by the CA.

DATASET: Project Management Data (WP1, Owners: KELADA, Coordinator and All Partners)	
Quality assurance process	All reports and deliverables are reviewed by Work Package Leaders and the Coordinator before submission.
Length of time of data re-usability	

WP7 Dissemination, communication and Exploitation data. Datasets obtained from dissemination, communication and exploitation are outline below:

DATASET: Reporting Database (WP7, Owner: MAGFI and ALL partners)										
DATA SUMMARY										
Purpose of the Data	<p>Magfi will collect data for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities.</p> <p>Specifically a stakeholder mapping exercise will be done.</p> <p>Also, data from social media channels and websites will be collected and analyzed to monitor the impact and efficiency of the CDE activities.</p>									
Type and Format of data	<p>Different data types will be collected.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Data type</th> <th>Format</th> <th>Types of documents</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Textual data, personnel and generic data</td> <td>MS office extensions files, .pdf, name, surname, email address, phone contact)</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deliverable reports, interim/periodic reports (.docx, .pdf) - Presentations at conferences, project/partner meetings (.pptx) - Meeting minutes (.docx, .pdf) </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Image data</td> <td>JPEG, PNG</td> <td>Tables, figures, diagrams, etc. (visualization of data and results)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Data type	Format	Types of documents	Textual data, personnel and generic data	MS office extensions files, .pdf, name, surname, email address, phone contact)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deliverable reports, interim/periodic reports (.docx, .pdf) - Presentations at conferences, project/partner meetings (.pptx) - Meeting minutes (.docx, .pdf) 	Image data	JPEG, PNG	Tables, figures, diagrams, etc. (visualization of data and results)
Data type	Format	Types of documents								
Textual data, personnel and generic data	MS office extensions files, .pdf, name, surname, email address, phone contact)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deliverable reports, interim/periodic reports (.docx, .pdf) - Presentations at conferences, project/partner meetings (.pptx) - Meeting minutes (.docx, .pdf) 								
Image data	JPEG, PNG	Tables, figures, diagrams, etc. (visualization of data and results)								
Reused-Data	Pre-existing contacts of Magfi team members and project partners can be used for CDE activities									
Data origin	Previous and/or current business activities, previous and/or current media channels used for other business activities or past and current EU funded projects by Magfi and project partners.									
Data size	Less than 500 MB									
Data Security and Storage	- MAGFI cloud									

DATASET: Reporting Database (WP7, Owner: MAGFI and ALL partners)

	- PROSPIGN Sharepoint
Data value (Long Term)	The data (text and figures) can be useful for the other project partners and other stakeholders. Non economic value
Making data FINDABLE, including provisions for metadata	
Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	The documents will be named according to the convention mentioned below. A text file describing this convention and other relevant information will be provided when the data is distributed.
Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	Reporting data will be named as mentioned below
Naming conventions used	Excel, Word, Pdf files are named with date YYYY.MM.DD - file title, for example 2024.05.01 Stakeholder mapping
Search keywords approach	Not required since information will be accessible by filtering (Excel doc) or by looking for a specific word (Word, Excel, pdf)
Clear versioning approach	Project deliverables templates have a history table. Other project working documents versions are understandable by the date in the file name.
Standards or procedures for metadata creation applied	NA
Making DATA openly ACCESSIBLE	
Data openly available or kept close	Deliverables marked as PUBLIC will be published in the project website once they are validated by EC. Stakeholder mapping including personal details will not be shared publicly to guarantee the privacy of the stakeholders. KERs will not be disclosed because of contractual reasons among the project partners

DATASET: Reporting Database (WP7, Owner: MAGFI and ALL partners)

How data will be made available	<p>Those data identified as PUBLIC will be disclosed via public deliverables on the project website.</p> <p>Data defined as SENSITIVE will be shared by Magfi only among project partners with a good reason supporting their request to share such data with them.</p>
Methods or SW tools for data access	MS office and PDF. SENSITIVE data will be shared with project partners only after a written request explaining the reason why they need such data.
SW documentation and other information needed	NA
Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	NA
Access restrictions	By default, the full data is restricted to the consortium. All data will be made available to partners on the PROSPIGN Sharepoint platform. The data access restriction is managed by the CA. (see WP1)
Making data INTEROPERABLE	
Data interoperability assessment	Magfi will collect and elaborate data for the purpose of the project implementation.
Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	
Data licensing for wide reuse	
Increase data RE-USE (through clarifying licenses)	
Timing of data availability for re-use (incl.	NA

DATASET: Reporting Database (WP7, Owner: MAGFI and ALL partners)

indications on embargo)	
Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	Data produced by Magfi and which may be re-used at the end of the project are the business leads which may be relevant for some project partners, mainly project Coordinator, for the purpose of exploitation of the project results/KER belonging to the same.
Restrictions to data re-use	Data will be as open as possible by default, as closed as necessary by exception The data personal data are not to be made available to the general public
Quality assurance process	Collected data will be verified at Magfi advisor and Director level. Every 12 months data will be checked, removing the obsolete data where evident.
Length of time of data re-usability	NA

- **Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded?**

Data which will be re-used within the **PROSPLIGN** project framework may include:

- Reactor and bioreactor process parameters data, analytical and material/samples characterization data, and Open access Python codes may be used during MVDA to test some machine learning algorithms which are not built-in to the SIMCA software or JMP (WP3).
- Some pre-existing datasets may be used for comparison and quality assurance purposes (MVDA activities). Existing Python scripts for signal acquisition and analysis will be used. These data are essentials for generating results to reach the project's goals (WP4).
- Activities related to the enzymatic lignin depolymerization led by University of Helsinki (WP3 and WP5) will re-use bacterial etherase sequences, commercial plasmids and microbial strains.
- Literature data, such as characterization data of already known compounds, will be used to identify known and unknown compounds isolated or synthesized (WP3 and WP5).

- **What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-use?**

The origin and provenance of data generated or reused are consigned in the [Table 2](#) below. In summary, the data generated or re-used originates from chemical and enzymatic lignin depolymerization processes (laboratory experiments) along with online and offline analytical tools (HPLC, NMR, MS etc.). Spectroscopic data can be NMR, MS and/or InfraRed spectra whereas chromatographic data would be HPLC compounds retention times, detector response factors and percentage of mixture composition. Additionally, data will originate from bioactivity experiments,

LCA and TEA investigations. Data will be generated from DoE (ANOVA table, statistical tests, model), MVDA models (model parameters, model metrics...), biological cytotoxicity assays, partners, literature, databases, researchers, stakeholders.

- **What is the expected size of the data that you will intend to generate or re-use?**

The size of data will be around **2TB** for the **PROSPLIGN** project. First, this value will depend on the number of trials being performed for each depolymerization schema (chemical or enzymatic). Secondly, batch duration will also have an impact on the size of the data. Finally, the critical quality attributes (**CQAs**) and critical material attributes (**CMAs**) collected during the experiments and the type of analytical characterization performed e.g. scanning electron microscopy analysis (photos) take more space during storage compared to a near infrared sample analysis (.csv or .xls generated table). Aspen Plus simulation files and results will be considered and will cover a certain size depending on the complexity of the simulation and the output results. The other WPs will generate a lot of multimedia files (see **Table 1**) along with computational scripts and signal processing files which can be memory consuming.

Table 2: Origin and size of data generated during the PROSPLIGN project

Contributing Partners	Relevant WP	Origin	Size
KELADA, UCD	WP3, WP5	literature, and experimental trials (spectroscopic data and HPLC)	The exact amount of these data has not yet been determined. 1-1000 GB (<1 GB, <100 files)
UCD	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	Research and experimental works, communication, SW related material (scripts, codes, layout...), LCA databases; literature study.	1 to 10 GB
UH	WP3, WP5	DNA sequencing and cloning, enzymes characterization, analytical tools (NMR, HPLC, MS)	Approximately 1TB
NOVA	WP4, WP5	Data obtained from panelist, experimental works, molecular, structural and chemical databases	The exact amount of these data has not yet been determined.

<i>Contributing Partners</i>	<i>Relevant WP</i>	<i>Origin</i>	<i>Size</i>
MEDINA	WP4, WP5	Biological cytotoxicity assays	The exact amount of these data has not yet been determined.
BFH	WP2, WP4	Analytical tools (LC, NMR) and chromatograms, structural characterization	Up to 3 GB

- **To whom might your data be useful (“data utility”) outside your project?**

Scientists, engineers, professors, corporations/companies, the general public etc. could benefit from the data generated during the project. For example, there is an increasing interest in chemical and bioprocess data in the scientific community, as these data will cover some aspects of process development, design and optimization. However, all data might not be open accessible due to IPR measures. Consequently, to align with the **IPR** requirements, data will be *“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”* for the purposes of exploitation.

4. Fair data

4.1. Making data findable including provisions for metadata

- **Are the data provided and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers, DOI)?**

Data will be reported in open-access publications and listed using standard convention (e.g. ACS Style guide). Standard identification mechanisms will be used as identifiers to enhance discoverability. **PROSPLIGN** data is discoverable within the consortium and between partners. Abbreviations and references used in each specific work package along with a list of keywords, **ORCID** for researchers and **DOI** for publications will serve as standard identification mechanisms. This latter (**DOI**) is an identifier employed by the European Commission (**EC**) open access repository - **Zenodo**. The datasets and other types of research outputs are then discoverable by humans and machine-readable metadata. **PROSPLIGN** will also comply with the EU obligation that any communication, documentation and publication activity related to the project must acknowledge the financial support of the EU. The following acknowledgement will be added to each publication and dataset description, thus facilitating identification and location of the data produced.

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Figure 3: EU acknowledgement picture to be used for a better data discoverability

To facilitate discoverability using a search engine, report documents contain an initial section depicting a list of abbreviations, keywords and references related to the **WP**. All data files must follow a specific naming convention to make them easily identifiable (see **Table 3**). The data are stored separately by type in different directories, e.g. samples management tables in a “samples management” directory, all Python scripts in a “scripts” directory.

In addition, University of Helsinki (**UH**) will use README-files template and perform modifications according to the type of experiments, metadata from datasets created with *Qvain* (www.qvain.fairdata.fi).

- **What disciplinary or general standards will be followed or in a case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what kind of metadata will be created and how?**

To enhance data discovery Data Cite Metadata schema will be followed. **DOI** is used for data and papers, **ORCID** for researchers (*see bullet point above*).

- **What naming convention do you follow?**

The data generated/collected or gathered by the partners will be named using the following naming convention (see **Table 3** below).

Table 3: Naming convention of data generated during the PROSPLIGN project

<i>Partner</i>	<i>WPs</i>	<i>Naming convention</i>	<i>Naming details</i>
KELADA, UCD	WP2, WP3, WP5	Compounds by IUPAC naming conventions. Experiments and associated data will be named according to a common convention	" PLGN_researcher initial_dd.mm.yyyy_### ". Example: Researcher AA runs their first experiment on 1st Jan 2024 would be labeled "PLGN_AA_01.01.2024_001"
UCD	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	[DDMMYY]_[Name]_[WPX]_SOURCE_VY.Z.[extension]	[DDMMYY]: Date, month and year [Name] : Document type or origin [WPX]: Work Package number SOURCE : e.g. Reactor, Bioreactor, Offline VY.Z. indicate the file version [extension] : file extension e.g. .xls, .csv or .usp (SIMCA), .py (Python)
UH	WP3 and WP5	commonly used naming policy incl. Title, date, version, person	<i>see KELADA naming convention above</i>

NOVA	WP4	(XX)_(DocumentName)_(ProjectName)_(yyyy-mm-dd).v(x.x)	<p>(XX): numerical characters unique artifact number within the folder indicating the artifact sequence</p> <p>v(x.x) indicates the artifact version. Version numbers "0.x" mean that the document hasn't been approved yet, minor changes will be reflected in the decimal (revision no) and major changes (formal reviews) in the version no.</p> <p>Example: D1.1_Project_Management_Guidelines_Prosplign_2024-03-25_v0.0</p>
MEDINA	WP4, WP5	MEDINA sample identifiers	<i>see KELADA naming convention above</i>
BFH	WP2, WP4	<p>The sourced For WP2 lignin will be labeled based on the provider and the number of lignin sources</p> <p>For WP4, the different fractions will be labeled based on the previous label of the sample</p>	<p>Example: For WP2 Seven (07) different lignins were sourced from Tanovis and labeled <i>TN01</i> to <i>TN07</i>.</p> <p>For WP4 if a depolymerized lignin mixture is received from KelAda labeled as "PLGN_AA_01.01.2024_001" for purification, the X different fractions will be labeled as "PLGN_AA_01.01.2024_001_frac1" to "PLGN_AA_01.01.2024_001_fracX"</p>

- **Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?**

Discovery of data will be enhanced using keywords provided in the metadata thus facilitating data re-use. However, as stated above data access may be restricted for intellectual property purposes. For example, these keywords will be used to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use:

- "pharmaceutical", "cosmetic", "bioorganic pharming", "fragrance", "chemistry", "molecule"
- "lignin", "sample prep", "bio-based", "bio-active"
- "column chromatography", "UV signals", "liquid chromatography", "LC", "NMR data"
- "depolymerization", "organic", "structural characterization", "method information"
- "MVDA", "PCA", "PLS", "MPCA", "DoE", "optimization", "lignin classification", "clustering", "multiblock"

- **Do you provide clear version numbers?**

Version numbers will be clearly outlined and documented in the README-files. Version numbers are provided in the file name. Draft versions will not be deleted and will instead be stored in “Superseded Versions” folder.

- **Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?**

Metadata will be harvested and indexed.

4.2. Making data openly accessible

- **Will all the data be openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why?**

Data will be as openly available as possible; however, restriction of usage may arise. The data produced and/or reused in the **PROSPIGN** project will be revised and approved by all consortium members before making them openly accessible.

All communication material will agree with the Horizon Europe guidelines and be made available in open access through Zenodo repository. Data will be openly available for group members and after publication to the general public.

Metadata will be open accessible; however, the dataset will be kept closed until public disclosure via journal, website etc. Data will be as open as possible and as closed as necessary.

The consortium may decide that some data should not be openly available before **IPR** protection or access is clarified. Besides, in the case of patent applications the accessibility of data will be restricted.

- **How will data be made available? Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?**

Data will be made openly available through different trusted repositories (See Section 7. Data Security) listed below:

- Openly accessible databases/Scientific journal (e.g.: HAL, MDPI)
- Public Online repository
 - <https://zenodo.org/>
 - HAL, ArXiv, OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>)
 - Kaggle, OpenMV, eigenvector (Popular open access repository platforms)
- Institutional/Academic websites
 - <https://access.olos.swiss/portal/home>
 - <https://www.bfh.ch/en/about-bfh/profile-values/open-science/>
 - www.ida.fairdata.fi (Long term storage)
 - www.prospign.eu/ and SharePoint by Microsoft available only for partners (**PROSPIGN**)
 - MEDINA data repository

However, all data might not be open accessible due to **IPR** measures. Consequently, to align with those deeds, data will be *“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”* for the purposes of exploitation.

- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

See above ([Section 4.1 Making data findable including provisions for metadata](#)).

- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents); specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible?**

The consortium may decide that some data should not be openly available before **IPR** protection or access is clarified. After clarification and discussion on **IPR** protection, data will be made available as soon as possible through scientific publications. Scientific publications require data collection, analysis and some literature review to corroborate the main findings. An embargo of +/- six (06) months may apply after the end of the project.

- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**

Yes, data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol (**HTTP** protocol, open-source code etc.). However, some licensed SW will be needed to access the data (see below).

- **What methods or SW tools are needed for data access?**

Several tools, methods and/or SW tools are needed for data access such as:

- Licensed SW such as Microsoft office suite (Excel, Word, PowerPoint), MATLAB (.mat files if applicable), OriginPro, MOE,
- Open-source **SW** such as Anaconda (Python), LibreOffice, Gromacs, Mendeley, Jupyter Notebook, RD kit
- Free and publicly accessible through repository and linked to publication. We will make these data publicly available via peer reviewed publications

- **Will documentation or reference about any SW be needed to access or read the data to be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant SW (e.g. Open-source code)?**

Documentation or any reference about any **SW** needed to access or read the data will be included provided that the relevant **SW** is open source.

- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**

All communication material will agree with the Horizon Europe guidelines and be made available open access through the open accessible channels listed above. The consortium may decide that some data should not be openly available before IP rights protection or access is clarified.

No restriction after disclosure, datasets will be as open as possible by default, as closed as necessary by exception.

4.3. Making data interoperable

- **What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?**
- **Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones? If not, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?**

To enhance data discovery Data Cite Metadata schema will be followed. Besides, standard identification mechanisms will be used as identifiers to make data interoperable to allow data exchange with other partners and across disciplines (scientific community). Datasets will be shared and/or deposited online in formats and types as aforementioned. During the project, the use of open-source SW is recommended, although for certain tasks licensed **SW** may be used when needed: JMP and SIMCA for **MVDA**, Aspen Plus for **LCA/TEA**. The interoperable concept demands that both data and metadata must be machine readable and that a consistent terminology is used. For open data, the repository in Zenodo will ensure interoperability. The metadata model used in Zenodo is based on Datacite's metadata schema that is compatible with the Dublin Core (<https://dublincore.org>) metadata standard and this can be interpreted by **OAI-PMH** (<https://www.openarchives.org>) harvesters like those used by OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>). However, as aforementioned, access to some data may be restricted and/or limited. All raw and processed data will be described in metadata README-files. Datasets will be stored in IDA, described and published with the help of *Qvain*, and the data can be searched using Etsin (<https://www.fairdata.fi/en/>).

For chemical compounds terminology the **IUPAC** (<https://iupac.org/>) regulations will be followed.

Data processing scripts will be coded using the freely available programming language Python and its established open-source libraries (including Pandas). Using the data and scripts is possible through open-source standard tools operable in different operating systems.

- **Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?**

Yes, the data will include qualified references (cross-references) to other data used in the **PROSPLIGN** project or from previous research.

4.4. Increase data re-use (through clarification license)

- **How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**

Documentation will be provided to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (See Section 4.1 Making data findable including provision for metadata).

- **Will the data produced in the project be usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**

Data produced during the project will be made available and usable by third parties even after the end of the project or after publication. Meta-data will be usable by third parties after the end of the project, but a 6-months embargo may apply. Datasets will be as open as possible by default, as closed as necessary by exception.

- **Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? How will data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?**

Data will be Open Accessible to permit the widest re-use possible (See channels mentioned above). They will be made available gradually as soon as articles are published. However, the consortium may decide that some data should not be openly available before **IPR** protection or access is clarified.

Data will be licensed to be as open as possible but closed when necessary.

- **Are there any data re-use restrictions?**

As stated above, data will be made available and open access by default. Data re-use restrictions may apply.

The **PROSPLIGN** cloud has a log of data assessment and several levels of security and user permissions, so that any restricted data is secure in that platform. Open data will be made accessible by following

¹ A Qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent (https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx)

Zenodo's guidelines for accessing the data. However, enzymes produced or purified during the activities of **WP3** will not be available for third parties.

- **Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?**

Yes, provenance of the data will be documented using the appropriate standards.

- **Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes**

The quality of the generated data will be guaranteed via the control and tracking of the data modifications by the consortium and other stakeholders.

- Quality assurance during data collection
 - Adequate calibration of apparatus and probes (raw material samples analysis, samples collected during lignin depolymerization, bioassay analysis using the corresponding standards tests, and validated protocols, internal/external reference and UV standards)
 - Batch replication and reproducibility (duplicate or triplicate) during depolymerization experiments
 - NMR spectra referenced against internal standards via standard practices and Free Induction Decay signal for NMR measurements
 - Mass spectrometer calibrated via standard reference compounds
 - Normal scientific quality procedures for DNA constructs and produced enzymes are followed
- Quality assurance on data collected
 - Assurance of data processing (data structure, preprocessing and cleaning)
 - Assurance of data integrity during sharing within the consortium and between partners
 - Assurance of data version tracking and defined nomenclature
 - The datasets will be reviewed by consortium and partners
- Quality assurance on data outputs (models, publications, dissemination etc.)
 - Python and/or MATLAB algorithms generated or reused as well as any software tested with other datasets to validate protocols and/or methodologies
 - Basic statistical analysis (normality, distribution, significance etc.) before and after analysis to check
 - Literature review and comparison to corroborate the main conclusions resulting from PROSPALIGN R&D activities
 - Publications, review, presentation reviewed by consortium members and partners.

- **For how long will the data be reusable?**

Data will be accessible and reusable for a minimum of 5 years. However, it is worth mentioning that depending on the **SW** used to generate or process data, the accessibility or reusability may be restricted. As an example, the SIMCA software scripts may not be available for reuse since this SW is not open access. Documentation or references related to SW needed to access or read the data will be included provided that the relevant **SW** is open source.

5. Other research outputs

These other research outputs are expected to be generated.

- Documents (scientific papers draft, DMP drafts, presentations)
- Emails and communications between the general public and stakeholders via www.prosplign.eu/
- Q&A collected during conferences, meetings; meetings reports and summary
- FAQs, downloads and viewing statistics (online repository)
- Reagents, bioactive molecules, bio-product (oxidized lignin), bio-actives mixtures
- Enzyme, strains, biocatalysts
- Procedures and methods (apparatus calibration, blank tests etc.)

A plan for how these other research outputs will be managed during and after the project and for how long these research outputs will be stored may be relevant.

6. Allocation of resources

- **What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ? How will these be covered?**

Costs related to open access to research data in Horizon Europe are eligible during the duration of the project under the conditions defined in the HE Grant Agreement.

- **Who will be responsible for data management in your project?**

Data management is part of WP1 with inputs from all other Work Packages within PROSPLIGN and is therefore implemented in all the project and management activities. KELADA, Project Coordinator, supported by UCD (as leader of MVDA and LCA activities) will be responsible for creating and maintaining the Data Management Plan, with inputs from all project partners.

- **How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?**

PROSPLIGN will comply with the **FAIR** principles during project timeline and thereafter, as mentioned in the **GA**, thus any direct financial resource is attributed to the storage and archiving.

SIMCA script reuse may generate cost and fees related to the renewal of the SIMCA software. The license purchased to support the project is valid for 3 years. The same situation is noted for the LCA activities where layouts and simulation results will be in Aspen Plus extension format (.apwz).

7.Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery, as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data).**

Data collected/generated in the project are first organized and stored by the data owners on their personal computers, or on the institutional/company's secured server(s) and/or hard drive(s), automatically backed-up on partners' respective secure servers according to their own data security policies. If not restricted for confidentiality purposes, in particular technical/pure lab data, data are also stored on the project's dedicated private file sharing space "PROSPLIGN SharePoint". Management-related data are by default securely stored on PROSPLIGN SharePoint and shared among all partners.

The **PROSPLIGN** SharePoint structuring solution, offering high security and easy interface, allows management of R&D projects and data within a secured environment. It is a key part of the knowledge management strategy implemented in the project and serves as a collaborative platform to ease document and information sharing. Partners log in with a private and secure username and password. Data is encoded and content access is managed by access rights policy. Partners can only see the contents they are allowed to access. All partners have project member rights and can access the project's key information: management / quality / meetings / communication documents, deliverables, certified documents (GA, DoA, PCA, etc.), Work Packages, etc.

Some activities will be carried out in a non-EU country (Switzerland). BFH External SSD (BFH IT services, Swiss Laws on data protection apply), online backup will be also used.

- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

The data collected/generated within the **PROSPLIGN** project and stored on either the partner institution's secured servers, automatically backed-up, or the **PROSPLIGN** SharePoint collaborative platform (depending on data restrictions criteria) will be kept for at least 5 years after the project ends so as to comply with Article 18 of the Grant Agreement: *"The beneficiaries must - for a period of five years after the payment of the balance - keep records and other supporting documentation in order to prove the proper implementation of the action and the costs they declare as eligible (...)"*.

8.Ethics

Personal data may be collected during events organized by partners (an example is the eventual attendance lists), and personnel data will be collected during the implementation of exploitation activities (relevant stakeholders' name, surname, email address, phone number).

9.Other issues

Not applicable.